

Smart Fishways: Real-time sensorization of fishways for autonomous assessment and management of their performance

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Introduction

The correct performance of fishways can be disrupted by multiple reasons, some avoidable (e.g. incorrect design or construction) and others manageable (e.g. the natural variability of rivers or incorrect maintenance). Any situation altering their design-performance affects biological response inside them and has the potential of hindering the free movement of fish.

Despite some malfunctions in fishways are difficult to solve, others are easily avoidable with the continuous monitoring of their performance (such as obstructions or discharge regulation).

This is where it comes into play the European Union's Horizon 2020 research project **Smart Fishways**, which aims to assess the effect of hydrological variability on stepped fishways and develop a technological and methodological framework to monitor fishways' performance in real-time. Among other the network is able to **optimize the timing of maintenance on a fishway** in real-time as well as help detecting those hydraulic configurations and times that maximize the fish passage.

Hardware and software architecture

Fig. 2 (a and b) One of the study sites and (c) Summary of software architecture

Up to day the Smart Fishways sensor network is composed of:

- 1) Multiple **water level monitoring nodes** (MS Ultra by GEA) installed over the different pools of a fishway.
- 2) A **multiparameter node** (MS Multi by GEA) able to measure the water depth, air and water temperature, luminosity, humidity, and barometric pressure.
- 3) A **pit-tag monitoring system** with multiple antennas (Half Duplex multiplexer reader, ORFID®, Portland, Oregon, USA).
- 4) A central **gateway** (Raspberry Pi + LoRa Radio + WiFi modem, by GEA).

The sensor network has a star architecture, it is the gateway that controls the nodes (python), runs the algorithms (python), collects the data (MySQL), triggers the alarms, and transmits the information online (HTTPS and MySQL (Figure 1.c)). Currently, the most interesting developed algorithms to improve the fishway management are “the real-time PIT-tag data processing algorithm” (under evaluation) and “the real-time obstruction detection algorithm” [1].

Fig. 2 Sensor network in Vadocondes fishway

Preliminary results and discussion

Fig. 4 shows part of the monitored data from 01/04/22 to 01/06/22 for Vadocondes fishway. Despite the short period, it is already possible to see the potential of the technology for monitoring and decision-making on the management of fishways. In the top part of the figure, results from the PIT-tag data processing algorithm are displayed for *Luciobarbus bocagei*, where key events in the fishway are easily identifiable: 1) a period with many fish movements associated with an increase in the river discharge, 2) a translocation of fish for experimental reasons, and 3) fish that are in the fishway and cannot be classified with a movement yet.

The sensors are able to collect **physical variables (on-site and on-line)** and near real-time with a configurable frequency. This allows **instantaneous data analysis** and ensures that **ongoing hydraulic scenarios are compatible with fish requirements**.

The observation and analysis of the data in real-time is vital to achieve an **adaptive management**, and to trigger scenarios that optimize the number of fish passages. Smart Fishways allows to easily and visually track historical events, reproduce them, make controlled tests, and immediately observe the biological responses. Likewise, it allows the **optimization of maintenance** [1], with the potential of automatizing and reducing the cost of this operations and, in the end, augmenting the service of fishways.

Fig. 4 Raw output of some monitored variables

